

Polymerized latik for retrieval of lead(II) from aqueous systems

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Manuscript received 26 December 2006, accepted 4 June 2007

Abstract : Latik, a solid residue obtained from virgin coconut oil processing industries was used as a precursor to produce formaldehyde polymerized latik bearing sulphonic acid functional group for retrieval of Pb^{II} from aqueous systems. The adsorptive potential of the adsorbent for Pb^{II} from aqueous solution was examined by the batch techniques. The parameters affecting Pb^{II} adsorption like concentration, agitation time, pH, sorbent dose and temperature were studied to establish optimum conditions for maximum adsorption. The surface modified latik adsorbs 95.7% Pb^{II} from an aqueous solution of 50 $\mu\text{mol dm}^{-3}$ concentration at 303 K. Different reagents were tested for extracting Pb^{II} from spent adsorbent and high extraction efficiency was obtained with 0.2 M HCl solution.

Keywords : Polymerized latik, adsorption, lead(II) removal.

Increased knowledge about ecotoxicological effects as well as increased legal requirement for reduction in industrial emissions necessitates research and development in the area of wastewater treatment¹. The presence of heavy metal ions in the environment and living systems is one of the major concerns, due to their toxicity to many life forms. Lead(II) is a highly toxic metal, considered as a priority pollutant. The origins of lead-containing wastewater are the effluents of mining areas, paper and pulp, battery, electroplating, alloys and lead smelting discharged into aquatic environments. To remove lead(II) from wastewater conventional methods such as chemical precipitation, chelation, reverse osmosis, ion exchange and adsorption are applicable. Adsorption of metal ions is currently of great interest as a possible and convenient method for scavenging metal ions from aqueous environment. In recent years there have been numerous researchers on the development of low cost adsorbents such as coconut husk², bituminous coal³, sphagnum moss peat⁴, marine macro algal biomass⁵ and banana pith⁶. In the present work, latik (a solid waste of virgin coconut oil production) has been used as a precursor material for the preparation of formaldehyde polymerized latik with sulphonic acid functionality (FPL) in removing lead(II) from water and wastewater. Virgin coconut oil (VCO) is the naturally processed product of fresh coconut meat⁷, which has many health benefits including raising body metabolism. It can decrease total cholesterol, fights against pathogens such as viruses, bacteria, fungus and a killing agent for intestinal parasites and improves thyroid function in patients having hypothyroidism. As more and more VCO is produced more and more latik is formed.

Fig. 1. Effect of pH on the adsorption of Pb^{II} onto FPL.

Results and discussion

The physical properties of FPL were determined by standard methods⁸. The values of zero point charge, apparent density, moisture content, ash content and particle size were 4.5, 1.37 g cm^{-3} , 2.5%, 1.9% and 0.096 mm respectively. The IR spectrum of FPL was obtained using KBr pellet technique between 4000–400 cm^{-1} . Some fundamental bands are 3410, 2925, 2854, 1746, 1602, 1384, 1351, 1160, 1020, 600 cm^{-1} . The FTIR spectrum of FPL shows a broad peak at 3410 cm^{-1} that is attributed to the overlapped bands arising from sulphonic acid hydroxyl and free phenolic hydroxyl groups. Additional peaks at 1160 cm^{-1} ($\nu_{\text{as}} \text{SO}_2$), 1020 cm^{-1} ($\nu_{\text{s}} \text{SO}_2$)

and 600 cm^{-1} (ν_{as} S-O) indicate the presence of $-\text{SO}_3\text{H}$ groups in FPL.

Effect of pH : The effect of pH was studied at constant adsorbent dosage (2.0 g dm^{-3}), ionic strength (0.01 M), shaking speed (200 rpm), particle size (0.096 mm) and temperature (303 K) for the sorbate concentration of 50 and $100\text{ }\mu\text{mol dm}^{-3}$. The amount of Pb^{II} adsorbed increased upto a pH value of 5.0 for both concentrations and then there is a slight decrease in the quantity of adsorption (Fig. 1). The possible sites on FPL for adsorption in acidic pH include H^+ ions from $-\text{SO}_3\text{H}$ functional group.

The pH_{zpc} of FPL was found to be 4.5 and below this pH surface charge of the adsorbent is positive. At low pH the predominant metal species [M^{2+} and $\text{M}(\text{OH})^+$] are positively charged. In the pH range of 2.0 – 4.5 the metal uptake is H^+ – M^{2+} exchange process. An increasing pH above pH_{zpc} shows a slight increase in adsorption at which the surface of the adsorbent is negatively charged and the metal species is still positively charged. The enhancing electrostatic attraction between positive metallic species and negative sorbent surface led to the increased adsorption of metal ions. Lower adsorption of lead(II), a cationic species at lower pH is apparently due to the higher concentration of H^+ ions present in the aqueous phase, which compete with Pb^{II} ions for the adsorption sites of FPL.

Table 1. Kinetic parameters for Pb^{II} adsorption onto FPL

Concn. ($\mu\text{mol dm}^{-3}$)	k_{ad} (min^{-1})	r^2
100	1.01×10^{-2}	0.983
200	1.13×10^{-2}	0.981
300	1.18×10^{-2}	0.987
450	1.14×10^{-2}	0.997
Temp. (K)		
303	1.01×10^{-2}	0.983
313	1.26×10^{-2}	0.981
323	1.57×10^{-2}	0.982
333	1.74×10^{-2}	0.989

The Pb^{II} adsorption onto FPL increased with contact time and initial concentration. The equilibrium condition was reached at an interval of 180.0 min for all initial concentrations and hence equilibrium time is independent of initial sorbate concentration. When the initial sorbate concentration increased from 100.0 to $400.0\text{ }\mu\text{mol dm}^{-3}$ the quantity adsorbed increased from 44.49 to $147.40\text{ }\mu\text{mol g}^{-1}$ while the adsorption percentage decreased from 89.0 to 73.7 .

Table 2. Isotherm constants for the adsorption of Pb^{II} onto FPL

Temp. (K)	Freundlich constants			Langmuir constants		
	K_F	n	r^2	b ($\text{dm}^{-3}\text{ }\mu\text{mol}^{-1}$)	Q^0 ($\mu\text{mol g}^{-1}$)	r^2
303	20.27	2.558	0.955	19.01	222.22	0.999
313	25.47	2.715	0.953	23.80	232.56	0.998
323	31.45	2.871	0.939	30.76	245.90	0.998
333	37.84	3.047	0.933	40.20	250.00	0.998

At constant pH the percentage adsorption increased from 64.0 to 99.8% for an increase in adsorbent concentration from 2.0 to 20.0 g dm^{-3} for the initial Pb^{II} concentration of $450.0\text{ }\mu\text{mol dm}^{-3}$. But the amount adsorbed per unit mass of the adsorbent decreased from 144.0 to $22.5\text{ }\mu\text{g g}^{-1}$. The highest adsorption density was shown by the adsorbent dose of 2.0 g dm^{-3} and therefore the entire studies were conducted at this mass to volume ratio.

Table 3. Values of thermodynamic parameters for the sorption of Pb^{2+} onto FPL

Temp. (K)	K_0	ΔG^0 (kJ mol^{-1})	ΔH^0 (kJ mol^{-1})	ΔS^0 ($\text{J mol}^{-1}\text{ K}^{-1}$)
303	2.11	-5.317		46.72
313	2.59	-6.737		45.23
			14.16	
323	3.05	-8.196		43.83
333	3.57	-9.715		42.51

Adsorption kinetics : The kinetic sorption data were used to calculate the first-order rate constant by assuming sorption interaction of the metal into FPL as a first order reaction. The kinetics of adsorption follows the first-order rate expression of Lagergren as shown in Fig. 2.

$$\log(q_e - q) = \log q_e - \frac{k_{\text{ad}} t}{2.303}$$

The straight line plots indicate the validity of the Lagergren equation describing the metal adsorption interaction onto FPL is of first-order. The kinetic parameters were optimized using the least square method and are given in Table 2. The values of k_{ad} at different initial concentrations clearly indicate that this parameter is totally independent of initial concentration. The nature of adsorption is endothermic since the values of k_{ad} increase with increase in temperature. The influence of temperature on the rate of adsorption of metal ions helps to compute activation energy (E_a) of the sorption process. The value of E_a calculated using Arrhenius equation was found to be 5.363 kJ mol^{-1} for Pb^{2+} adsorption onto FPL indicating that intraparticle diffusion might have been the essential rate-limiting step in the sorption process.

Intraparticle transport phenomenon : Plot of q_t , amount of Pb^{II} adsorbed per unit mass of adsorbent versus $t^{1/2}$, square root of time (Fig. 3) is commonly used to assess the role of diffusion in the adsorption process. The rate constants for the intraparticle diffusion (k_{id}) for $200 \mu\text{mol dm}^{-3}$ were calculated from the slope of the linear portion of the plots. As the temperature increased from 303 to 333 K, k_{id} values increased gradually from 4.33 to $5.73 \mu\text{mol g}^{-1} \text{min}^{-1/2}$. From these results it is clear that the values of k_{id} increases with increasing temperature. As the temperature increases a gradual decline in the retarding forces acting on the diffusing ions take place, which in turn, increases the value of k_{id} . It can also be seen that the boundary layer diffusion increased with increase in the initial metal ion concentration. The plots are linear for a wide range of contact time and they do not pass through the origin indicating that the process of adsorption is not solely governed by intraparticle diffusion but by other modes of adsorption simultaneously operating in the system.

Fig. 2. Lagergren plots for the adsorption of Pb^{II} onto FPL.

Equilibrium isotherm studies : Adsorption isotherms are angular, positive and concave to the concentration axis. Initially the adsorption is quite rapid which is followed by a

slow approach to equilibrium of high metal ion concentration. The results indicate the utility of the adsorbent for a wide range of concentration. The equilibrium data for the adsorption of Pb^{II} in the concentration range of $100\text{--}900 \mu\text{mol dm}^{-3}$ onto FPL at different temperature from 303 to 333 K were analyzed using Langmuir and Freundlich models. Out of the two models, the Langmuir isotherm followed better with the values of regression coefficient ($r^2 > 0.998$). The mechanistic parameters were evaluated and are given in Table 2. The values show that the sorption process is thermodynamically feasible.

Variation of thermodynamic equilibrium constant (K_o) with temperature for the sorption reaction was calculated by the method of Biggar and Cheung⁹ as applied by Varshney *et al.*¹⁰. As the concentration of solute approaches zero, the activity coefficient (γ) approaches unity. By plotting $\ln(C_e/q_e)$ versus q_e and extrapolating to zero q_e (Fig. 4) the value of K_o is obtained. The positive value of ΔH° confirms the endothermic nature of the adsorption process. As diffusion is an endothermic process it would be expected that increased solution temperature would result in an increased uptake of Pb^{II} ions from solutions. The free energy change becomes more and more negative with raise in temperature and the values are indicating the spontaneous nature of the adsorption process (Table 3). The entropy factor is also favourable indicating the increased randomness at the solid solution interface during adsorption.

Extraction and regeneration :

Using 0.1 g Pb^{II} loaded FPL extraction studies were conducted using a series of reagents. Minimum desorption (22.8%) was observed when distilled water was used. But

Fig. 3. Intraparticle diffusion plots for the adsorption of Pb^{II} onto FPL.

Fig. 4. Plots of $\ln(q_e/C_e)$ versus q_e for the adsorption of Pb^{II} onto FPL.

92.0% of adsorbed Pb^{II} was extractable with 0.2 M HCl. The regenerated adsorbent was found to be reusable.

Conclusion :

The objective of the study was to investigate the feasibility of using formaldehyde polymerized latik having sulphonic acid functionality for the removal of Pb^{II} ions from aqueous solutions. The batch experiments show that the adsorption of Pb^{II} onto FPL is dependent on pH, amount of adsorbent, concentration, contact time and temperature. Above 95% adsorption was observed at lower concentration. The Lagergren pseudo-first order rate expression could be used to fit the kinetic data. The adsorption was found to be endothermic in nature. Adsorption of Pb^{II} followed the Langmuir model as evidenced from better coefficient of the correlation values. Parameter obtained from Pb^{II} -FPL system confirm the feasibility of the process. The adsorbed Pb^{II} desorbed quantitatively by 0.2 M HCl and the adsorbent can be reused for subsequent cycles. This is a cost-effective and

efficient way of removal of Pb^{II} from wastewater using chemically modified latik.

Experimental

Latik is the protienaceous material left after the extraction of virgin coconut oil from coconut kernel. It is then defatted with ethanol-toluene mixture. The sample was then treated with a mixture of 0.2 N sulphuric acid and 39.0% formaldehyde¹¹ for about 6.0 h with occasional stirring. The product (FPL) was then washed several times with distilled water, dried at 333–353 K, powdered and sieved to get particles of average size 0.096 mm.

Batch experiments were conducted with FPL to evaluate the extent of Pb^{II} removal from aqueous solutions under a wide range of conditions such as contact time, pH, initial Pb^{II} concentration, temperature etc. After separating the adsorbent Pb^{II} was estimated using Perkin-Elmer model 2380 atomic absorption spectrophotometer.

Acknowledgement

The Head of Chemistry Department of Government Arts College, Thiruvananthapuram is gratefully acknowledged for providing laboratory facilities.

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